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An Analysis of Risk, Return, and the Volatility of Selected Banks Listed on Nifty50 Stock Market

Dr. Poornima Vijaykumar

Elizabeth Joseph

ORCID ID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-4663-3885>

Associate Professor
UG & PG Deptt. of Commerce & Management
St. Joseph's College of Commerce (Autonomous)
#163, Brigade Road, Bengaluru 560025

Auditor at Ernst and Young (EY GDS)
Bengaluru, India.

Abstract

Understanding the risk and return and the volatility of the stock prices are important factors for an investor to become an efficient investor and a good decision-maker. The aim of this research is to analyze the risk and return of stock prices, as well as the volatility of stocks, in the banking sector, with a focus on helping investors and bank management make informed decisions. The study examines these factors for banking sector stocks listed on Nifty50, a national stock exchange, over a seven-year period from April 1, 2015, to February 28, 2022. The research utilizes the coefficient of variance to measure stock volatility, beta and standard deviation to identify risk, and employs multiple linear regression and one-sample t-test for analysis. The findings indicate that while there was no significant increase in the risk and return of banking sector stocks, there was a significant increase in their volatility. Despite the perceived reliability of banking sector stocks among investors, the study highlights the inherent risks of investing in the stock market. The results of this study can guide investors in making informed decisions regarding their investments in the banking sector stocks.

Keywords: Stock Prices, Risk, Return, Volatility, and Banking Sector.

INTRODUCTION:

The stock market serves as a platform where investors and traders can buy and sell shares of both private and public companies. Listing shares in the stock market can significantly benefit a company's financial position (Vijayakumar & Mahadev, 2019). Investing in the stock market offers the potential for rapid growth compared to other investment avenues, but it comes with inherent risks due to the market's volatility, which is often influenced by economic uncertainties.

Among the various sectors in the stock market, the banking sector is often perceived as a safe investment option by many investors. However, it is crucial to analyze the risk, return, and volatility associated with banking sector stocks before making investment decisions.

The researcher has chosen to focus on five key banking sector stocks: Housing Development Finance Corporation Limited, Industrial Credit and Investment Corporation of India, Kotak Mahindra Bank Limited, State Bank of India, and Axis Bank. These selections were made due to the significant role of the banking sector in the development of the Indian economy. Any impact on the banking sector, whether from internal factors or external obstacles, can affect the volatility of these banks' stock prices, thereby influencing investors' decisions and investment patterns.

Globalization has led to the integration of financial markets, particularly in the banking sector, resulting in the introduction of new technologies and a decrease in fraudulent activities. This digitalization has enhanced customer experiences, leading to stronger bank-customer relationships. Top of Form

Stock Market:

The international monetary system operates under a floating exchange rate system, where currency exchange rates are determined by supply and demand. Similarly, stock prices are driven by these same forces of supply and demand. Investing in the stock market offers the potential for high returns compared to other investment methods. However, it is also considered risky, as there is no guarantee on the invested amount. Stock prices fluctuate due to changes in demand and supply, and unforeseen events in the market or economy can lead to price variances. Nevertheless, the stock market generally offers higher returns than fixed deposits and other investments, albeit with higher risk. Investing in the stock market requires accepting a certain level of risk that cannot be eliminated (systematic risk), but unsystematic risk can be managed through wise stock selection.

Stock markets play a vital role in the economy by facilitating the buying and selling of financial securities. Investors can sell their stocks at any time, providing liquidity and easing liquidity risk. Stock prices can fluctuate randomly due to changing demand and supply dynamics. Publicly listed companies trade their stocks on stock exchanges, such as the Bombay Stock Exchange (BSE) and the National Stock Exchange (NSE). The primary market involves the issuance of new securities to raise capital, while the secondary market allows for the trading of existing securities.

Global Stock Market:

The world's first recognized stock market system was established in Antwerp, Belgium, although actual stock trading did not occur (bebusinessed, 2018). The Dutch East India Company is considered the first publicly traded company, establishing modern stock trading in Amsterdam in 1611. India's SEBI (Securities and Exchange Board of India) regulates the primary and

secondary stock markets, ensuring fair and transparent trading practices.

Indian Stock Market:

India's stock market includes the Bombay Stock Exchange (BSE) and the National Stock Exchange (NSE). BSE, Asia's first stock exchange established in 1875, introduced the BSE Sensex as a measure of its overall performance. NSE, launched in 1992, aims to simplify investor participation. Both exchanges list stocks of companies across various sectors, with Nifty50 being NSE's flagship index comprising 50 stocks from key sectors of the Indian economy.

Banking Sector:

Banking traces its roots back to money lending and exchange. The first investment and merchant bank was established in the middle ages by Italian grain merchants (Roussakis, 1997). Banking practices evolved, promoting commercial and industrial growth and making money supply more responsive. The banking sector witnessed significant growth in the 1980s following financial market deregulation in many countries.

Banking Sector in India:

India's banking sector is considered the backbone of the economy (Jape, & Pauldhas, 2021). It originated in the late 18th century, with the General Bank of India and Bank of Hindustan being among the first banks. State Bank of India, established in 1806, is the oldest surviving bank. Banks in India provide various financial services, including loans, deposits, and digital banking. The sector includes commercial banks, small finance banks, payment banks, regional rural banks, and co-operative banks (Agarwal, & Somani, 2021).

Historical Background of Selected Banking Sectors:

The selected banks for this research are Housing Development Finance Corporation Limited (HDFC), Industrial Credit and Investment Corporation of India (ICICI), Kotak Mahindra Bank, State Bank of India (SBI), and Axis Bank. HDFC, established in 1994, is India's largest private sector bank, focusing on home loans and related credit facilities. ICICI, founded in 1994, aimed to provide medium and long-term project financing. Kotak Mahindra Bank, established in 2003, was the first non-banking company in India to convert to a banking company. SBI traces its origins back to the Bank of Calcutta in 1806. Axis Bank, founded in 1993, is the third-largest private sector bank in India.

Risk and Return:

Understanding the risk and return of stocks is crucial for investors. Beta and standard deviation help assess the risk associated with stocks. Higher beta indicates higher risk and return, while lower beta signifies lower risk and return. Diversifying investments across different companies can reduce risk. Monitoring the financial performance of the banking sector in the stock market is essential for investors and bank management to make informed investment decisions.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Jogheel, Mehta, Baskaran, Suryanarayanan, and Devi (2021) conducted a study on the risk and return analysis of selected banking securities, focusing on the relationship between the Sensex and securities to identify the best investment options among seven banks. Using secondary data and metrics like standard deviation, average return, variance, correlation, and beta value, they concluded that Kotak Bank offered higher returns at lower risk compared to other banks. Niewińska (2020) examined factors influencing stock return volatility in the euro zone banking sector, analyzing internal and external historical determinants using a static panel model and data from 2004 to 2015. The study confirmed the significant impact of selected factors on volatility. Meda Srinivasa Rao, Podile, and Navvula (2020) analyzed the risk and return of selected Nifty banks stocks, comparing them between different political administrations and public versus private sector banks from 2010 to 2019. They suggested investing in Youth Enterprise Scheme Bank for higher risk and returns and in Kotak Mahindra Bank or Housing Development Finance Corporation bank Limited for lower risk. Shahani and Nagpal (2019) studied the movement of interest rates and spillover of volatility and returns among leading bank stocks in India from 2013 to 2018. They found that interest rate changes did not significantly affect bank stock returns. Suresh and Sai Prakash (2018) compared the risk-return analysis of public and private sector banks listed on Bank Nifty from 2016, suggesting investors avoid stocks with higher beta values. Savsani and Rathod (2018) analyzed the risk-return relationship of Sensex and banking sector stocks using secondary data over 13 years, focusing on four banking sector stocks, while Gautami and Kalyan (2018) conducted a comparative study on risk and return analysis of selected stocks in India, recommending stocks with lower coefficient of variation for investment. Anbukarasi and Devaki (2017) studied the volatility of foreign institutional investments on stock return of selected banking companies listed in BSE from 2007 to 2016, and Kedia (2016) examined the determinants of profitability of Indian public sector banks from 2006 to 2013. Patjoshi (2016) conducted a comparative risk and return analysis of Bombay stock market with selected banking stocks in India from 2001 to 2015, and Singh and Makkar (2014) explored the relationship between crisis and stock volatility in the Indian banking sector from 2004 to 2012.

In conclusion, the reviewed literature provides valuable insights into the risk and return dynamics of banking securities and stocks in various contexts. Studies have utilized a range of analytical tools and datasets to assess factors influencing stock volatility, compare performance across different banks and sectors, and analyze the impact of external factors like political changes and crises. The findings highlight the importance of considering various factors such as beta values, historical determinants, and interest rate movements when making investment decisions in the banking sector. Overall, these studies contribute to the understanding of risk-return trade-offs and offer valuable implications for investors and policymakers in the banking and financial sectors.

Research Design

Statement of the Problem

Despite the popularity of investing in banking sector stocks among investors, there exists a hesitation to fully engage in such investments due to perceived volatility and associated risks. This study aims to address this issue by analyzing the risk, return, and volatility of banks listed on the Nifty50 Stock Market. By providing insights into these aspects, the study seeks to empower both bank management and investors to make informed decisions, ultimately enhancing their investment strategies and outcomes.

Need and Importance of the Study

Analyzing stock volatility, risk, and return is crucial for efficient investment decision-making. This research aims to help investors avoid unsystematic risk and make informed decisions to minimize risk and maximize returns in the stock market, particularly in the banking sector.

Objectives of the Study

1. To assess the risk and return of selected banking sector stocks.
2. To examine the volatility and fluctuations of selected banking sector stocks.

Hypotheses of the Study

1. H_0 1: There is no significant increase in the risk and return of banking sector stocks.
 H_a 1: There is a significant increase in the risk and return of banking sector stocks.
2. H_0 2: There is no significant increase in the volatility of banking sector stocks.
 H_a 2: There is a significant increase in the volatility of banking sector stocks.

Conceptual Framework

Figure 1 Conceptual Framework Measuring Return & Risk

Scope of the Study

The study focuses on five banks listed on Nifty50, namely Housing Development Finance Corporation Limited, Industrial Credit and Investment Corporation of India, Kotak Mahindra Bank Ltd, Axis Bank, and State Bank of India, to assess risk, return, and volatility.

Sources of Data

Data for the study was collected from secondary sources, including Nifty50, Yahoo Finance, and Money Control, over a period of seven years from April 2015 to February 2022. Statistical analysis was performed using Excel and SPSS.

Statistical Analysis

The statistical analysis conducted in this study focused on understanding the risk, return, and volatility of selected banking sector stocks listed on the Nifty50 stock market over a period of seven years. The coefficient of variation (CV) was used to assess the volatility of the stocks, with higher values indicating greater volatility. Beta (β) was calculated to determine the systematic risk and volatility of the stocks relative to the market, with values above 1 indicating higher risk. Daily returns of the stocks were calculated using the opening and closing stock prices, and metrics such as average return, standard deviation, and variance were analyzed to understand past performance. Multiple linear regression analysis was employed to examine the relationship between stock returns (dependent variable) and risk factors like beta and standard deviation (independent variables). Additionally, a one-sample t-test was used to assess the volatility of the stocks based on the coefficient of variation. These statistical techniques provided valuable insights for investors and bank management in making informed decisions regarding investment in banking sector stocks. The researcher employed the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS version 23) software to perform the analysis.

Limitations of the Study

Limitations of this study include the small sample size, which focused on only five stocks listed on the Nifty50. Additionally, the study's timeframe was restricted, potentially limiting the generalizability of the findings. While the statistical techniques used were appropriate, the adoption of more advanced model testing tools could have enhanced the robustness of the results. Furthermore, conclusions and inferences were drawn solely based on secondary data, which may introduce biases or limitations in the analysis.

ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

I. ANALYSIS OF RETURN OF THE STOCKS FOR A PERIOD OF SEVEN YEARS

Table 1 Showing Return of Housing Development Finance Corporation Bank Ltd.

Year (HDFC Bank Ltd.)	Opening Stock Price (P0)	Adjusted Closing Price (P1)	P1-P0	Return (R) $\frac{p1 - p0}{p0} \times 100$
2015-2016	513.05	517.7225	4.6725	0.9107
2016-2017	534.4	702.9551	168.5551	31.5409
2017-2018	732	925.2043	193.2043	26.3940
2018-2019	945.25	1136.827	191.577	20.2673
2019-2020	1162.625	858.1858	(304.4392)	(26.1855)
2020-2021	863.85	1487.213	623.363	72.1610
2021-2022	1499.4	1426.25	(73.15)	(4.8786)
Total Return (ΣR)				120.2098
Average Return ($\frac{\Sigma R}{N}$)				17.17282

Source: Author's calculation based on secondary data

The calculations presented in this research are grounded in the findings of a study titled "A Comparative Study on Risk and Return Analysis of Selected Stocks in India," authored by Dr. S. Gautami and Dr. Nalla Bala Kalyan.

$$\text{Return} = \frac{\text{Adjusted closing stock price} - \text{opening stock price}}{\text{opening stock price}} \times 100$$

Total return = 120.2098

$$\text{Average return} = \frac{\text{Total return}}{N}$$

N = Sample size

$$\text{Average return} = \frac{120.2098}{7} = 17.17282$$

Interpretation:

From the above Table 1, the total return of the Housing Development Finance Corporation Bank Limited is 120.2098 and the average return is 17.17282 during the period of study.

Table 2 Showing Return of Industrial Credit and Investment Corporation of India Bank Ltd.

Year	Opening Stock Price (P0)	Adjusted Closing Price (P1)	P1-P0	Return (R)
2015-2016	286.3636	204.3223	(82.0413)	(28.6493)
2016-2017	214.5455	243.9502	29.4047	13.70558
2017-2018	253.4545	271.9195	18.465	7.285331
2018-2019	273	397.439	124.439	45.58205
2019-2020	401.45	322.8048	(78.6452)	(19.5903)
2020-2021	319	580.4005	261.4005	81.94373
2021-2022	587.55	742.7000	155.15	26.40626
Total Return ($\sum R$)				126.6833
Average Return ($\frac{\sum R}{N}$)				31.67083

Source: Author's Calculation based on Secondary Data

$$\text{Average return} = \frac{\sum R}{N} = \frac{126.6833}{7} = 31.67083$$

Interpretation:

From the above Table 2, the total return of the ICICI Bank Ltd is 126.6833 and the average return is 31.67083, during the period of study.

Table 3 Showing Return of Kotak Mahindra Bank Ltd.

Year	Opening Stock Price (P0)	Adjusted Closing Price (P1)	P1-P0	Return
2015-2016	661.45	678.7354	17.2854	2.613259
2016-2017	682	772.4706	90.4706	13.26548
2017-2018	777.5	1046.182	268.682	34.55717
2018-2019	1049.05	1339.363	290.313	27.6739
2019-2020	1336	1295.407	(40.593)	(3.0384)
2020-2021	1294.9	1752.13	457.23	35.31006
2021-2022	1770	1842.75	72.75	4.110169
Total Return ($\sum R$)				114.4916
Average Return ($\frac{\sum R}{N}$)				16.35595

Source: Author's calculation based on secondary data

$$\text{Average return} = \frac{\sum R}{N} = \frac{114.4916}{7} = 16.35595$$

Interpretation:

From the above Table 3, the total return of Kotak Mahindra Bank Ltd is 114.4916 and its average return is 16.35595, during the period of study.

Table 4 Showing Return of State Bank of India

Year	Opening Stock Price (P0)	Adjusted Closing Price (P1)	P1-P0	Return
2015-2016	266.65	194.25	(72.4)	(27.1517)
2016-2017	193.7	293.4	99.7	51.47135
2017-2018	294.8	249.9	(44.9)	(15.2307)
2018-2019	251.8	319	67.2	26.68785
2019-2020	321.8	196.85	(124.95)	(38.8285)
2020-2021	194	364.3	170.3	87.78351
2021-2022	367.7	483.2	115.5	31.41148
Total Return ($\sum R$)				116.1434
Average Returns ($\frac{\sum R}{N}$)				16.59191

Source: Author's calculation based on secondary data

$$\text{Average return} = \frac{\sum R}{N} = \frac{116.1434}{7} = 16.59191$$

Interpretation:

From the above Table 4 the total return of State Bank of India is 116.1434 and its average return is 16.59191, during the period of study.

Table 5 Showing Return of Axis Bank

Year	Opening Stock Price (P0)	Adjusted Closing Price (P1)	P1-P0	Return
2015-2016	557.7	435.2134	(122.487)	(21.9628)
2016-2017	440.9	485.4219	44.5219	10.09796
2017-2018	495.7	509.8668	14.1668	2.857938
2018-2019	506.75	779.7316	272.9816	53.86909
2019-2020	780.95	379	(401.95)	(51.4694)
2020-2021	376.25	697.45	321.2	85.36877
2021-2022	706.3	742.4	36.1	5.111143
Total Return ($\sum R$)				83.87272
Average Return ($\frac{\sum R}{N}$)				11.98182

Source: Author's calculation based on secondary data

$$\text{Average return} = \frac{\sum R}{N} = \frac{83.87272}{7} = 11.98182$$

Interpretation:

From the above Table 5, the total return of Axis Bank is 83.87272 and its average return is 11.98182, during the period of study.

II. ANALYSIS SHOWING CALCULATION OF STANDARD DEVIATION (RISK)

Table 6 Showing Calculation of Standard Deviation of Housing Development Finance Corporation Bank Limited in Percentage (%) for a Period of Seven Years

Year	Return (R)	Average Return (\bar{R})	D = R - \bar{R}	D ²
2015-2016	0.9107	17.17282	(16.2623)	264.4624
2016-2017	31.5409	17.17282	14.3679	206.4366
2017-2018	26.3940	17.17282	9.221	85.02684
2018-2019	20.2673	17.17282	3.0943	9.574692
2019-2020	(26.1855)	17.17282	(43.3585)	1879.96
2020-2021	72.1610	17.17282	54.988	3023.68
2021-2022	(4.8786)	17.17282	(22.0516)	486.2731
ΣD^2				5955.413

Source: Author's calculation based on secondary data

$$\text{Variance} = \frac{\Sigma D^2}{N-1}$$

$$\text{Variance} = \frac{5955.431}{7-1} = \frac{5955.431}{6} = 992.5689$$

$$\text{Standard deviation} = \sqrt{\text{variance}} = \sqrt{992.5689} = 31.50506$$

Interpretation:

From the above Table 6, standard deviation of the Housing Development Finance Corporation bank Limited is 31.50506 and its variance is 992.5689.

Table 7 Showing Calculation of Standard Deviation of Industrial Credit and Investment Corporation of India Bank Ltd in Percentage for a Period of Seven Years

Year	Return (R)	Average Return (\bar{R})	D = R - \bar{R}	D ²
2015-2016	(28.6493)	31.67083	(60.32013)	3638.518083
2016-2017	13.70558	31.67083	(17.96525)	322.7502076
2017-2018	7.285331	31.67083	(24.385499)	594.6525615
2018-2019	45.58205	31.67083	13.91122	193.5220419
2019-2020	(19.5903)	31.67083	(51.26113)	2627.703449
2020-2021	81.94373	31.67083	50.2729	2527.364474
2021-2022	26.40626	31.67083	(5.26457)	27.71569728
ΣD^2				9932.226515

Source: Author's calculation based on secondary data

$$\text{Variance} = \frac{\Sigma D^2}{N-1} = \frac{9932.226515}{6} = 1655.3371086$$

$$\text{Standard deviation} = \sqrt{\text{variance}} = \sqrt{1655.3371086} = 40.6862518$$

Interpretation:

From the above Table 7, standard deviation of ICICI Bank Ltd is 40.6862518 and its variance is 1655.3371086.

Table 8 Showing Calculation of Standard Deviation of Kotak Mahindra Bank Ltd. in Percentage for a Period of Seven Years

Year	Return (R)	Average Return (\bar{R})	D = R - \bar{R}	D ²
2015-2016	2.613259	16.35595	(13.742691)	188.8615559
2016-2017	13.26548	16.35595	(3.09047)	9.551004821
2017-2018	34.55717	16.35595	18.20122	331.2844095
2018-2019	27.6739	16.35595	11.31795	128.0959922
2019-2020	(3.0384)	16.35595	(19.39435)	376.1408119
2020-2021	35.31006	16.35595	18.95411	359.2582859
2021-2022	4.110169	16.35595	(12.245781)	149.9591523
ΣD^2				1543.151213

Source: Author's calculation based on secondary data

$$\text{Variance} = \frac{\Sigma D^2}{N-1} = \frac{1543.151213}{6} = 257.1918688$$

$$\text{Standard deviation} = \sqrt{\text{Variance}} = \sqrt{257.1918688} = 16.03720265$$

Interpretation:

From the above Table 8, standard deviation of Kotak Mahindra Bank is 16.03720265 and its variance is 257.1918688.

Table 9 Showing Calculation of Standard Deviation of State Bank of India in Percentage for a Period of Seven Years

Year	Return (R)	Average Return (\bar{R})	D = R - \bar{R}	D ²
2015-2016	(27.1517)	16.59191	(43.74361)	1913.503
2016-2017	51.47135	16.59191	34.87944	1216.575
2017-2018	(15.2307)	16.59191	(31.82261)	1012.679
2018-2019	26.68785	16.59191	10.09594	101.928
2019-2020	(38.8285)	16.59191	(55.42041)	3071.422
2020-2021	87.78351	16.59191	71.1916	5068.244
2021-2022	31.41148	16.59191	14.81957	219.6197
ΣD^2				12603.97

Source: Author's calculation based on secondary data

$$\text{Variance} = \frac{\Sigma D^2}{N-1} = \frac{12603.97}{6} = 2100.662$$

$$\text{Standard deviation} = \sqrt{\text{variance}} = \sqrt{2100.662} = 45.83298$$

Interpretation:

From the above Table 9, the standard deviation of SBI is 45.83298 and its variance is 2100.662.

Table 10 Showing Calculation of Standard Deviation of Axis Bank Ltd in Percentage for a Period of Seven Years

Year	Return (R)	Average Return (\bar{R})	D = R - \bar{R}	D ²
2015-2016	(21.9628)	11.98182	(33.94462)	1152.237
2016-2017	10.09796	11.98182	(1.88386)	3.548928
2017-2018	2.857938	11.98182	(9.123882)	83.24522
2018-2019	53.86909	11.98182	41.88727	1754.543
2019-2020	(51.4694)	11.98182	(63.45122)	4026.057
2020-2021	85.36877	11.98182	73.38695	5385.644
2021-2022	5.111143	11.98182	(6.870677)	47.2062
ΣD^2				12452.48

Source: Author's calculation based on secondary data

$$\text{Variance} = \frac{\Sigma D^2}{N-1} = \frac{12452.48}{6} = 2075.414$$

$$\text{Standard deviation} = \sqrt{\text{Variance}} = \sqrt{2075.414} = 45.55671$$

Interpretation:

From the above Table 10, standard deviation of Axis Bank is 45.55671 and its variance is 2075.414.

III. ANALYSIS SHOWING CALCULATION OF COEFFICIENT OF VARIATION

Coefficient of variation has been calculated to understand the volatility and fluctuations of the selected banking sector stocks.

Table 11 Showing Calculation of Coefficient of Variation of the Selected Banking Sector Stocks for a Period of Seven Years

Banks	Standard Deviation (risk)	Average Returns	Coefficient of variation
HDFC Bank	17.173	31.50506	1.834569382
ICICI Bank	31.67083	40.6862518	1.284660105
Kotak Mahindra Bank	16.35595	16.03720265	0.980511841
SBI	16.59191	45.83298	2.76236913
Axis Bank	11.98182	45.55671	3.802152761

Source: Author's calculation based on secondary data

Interpretation:

From the above Table 11, Axis Bank had the highest coefficient of variation for a total of seven years. Its coefficient variation was 3.802152761 which indicate that the axis bank is more volatile in nature compared to the other banks.

IV. RESULTS OF ONE SAMPLE T-TEST

To assess the hypothesis regarding the volatility of banking sector stocks, a one-sample t-test was employed by the researcher. This statistical test was chosen to determine if there was a notable difference between the mean volatility of the sample and that of the population. The analysis yielded two key tables: one displaying the one-sample statistics and the other showing the results of the one-sample t-test.

H₀: There is no significant increase in the volatility of the banking sector stocks.

H_a: There is significant increase in the volatility of the banking sector stocks.

Table 12 Showing Results of One-Sample Statistics

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Coefficient of variation	5	2.13285260	1.153163841	.515710547

Source: Author's calculation based on secondary data

Table 13 Showing Results of One-Sample Test

	Test Value = 0					
	t	df	Significance. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
					Lower	Upper
Coefficient of variation	4.136	4	0.014	2.132852600	.70101057	3.56469463

Source: Author's calculation based on secondary data

Interpretation:

From the above Table 13, one sample t-test was conducted to prove the hypothesis used for this study. It was used to understand the significant level of increase in the volatility of the banking sector stocks. The sample size used in one sample t-test were five banks. Table 12 one sample statistics revealed the mean value as 2.13285260 and the standard deviation as 1.153163841. The significance 2-tailed value over the p-value was 0.014 which is less than 0.05. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected and the alternative hypothesis is accepted in the study. It indicates that there is a significant increase in the volatility of the banking sector stocks.

Table 14: Summary Results of all Calculations for a Period of Seven Years

Statistical Tools	HDFC Bank	ICICI Bank	Kotak Mahindra Bank	SBI	Axis Bank
Average Returns	17.173	31.67083	16.35595	16.59191	11.98182
Standard Deviation (risk)	31.50506	40.6862518	16.03720265	45.83298	45.55671
Variance	992.5689	1655.371086	257.1918688	2100.662	2075.414
Beta	0.97351	1.148189	0.383842774	1.39510442	1.387652599
Coefficient of variation	1.834569	1.28466	0.980512	2.762369	3.802153

Source: Author's calculation based on secondary data

Interpretation:

From the above Table 14, the average return is high in ICICI Bank and less in Axis bank. By calculating the beta and standard deviation, the risk is higher in State Bank of India and lesser in Kotak Mahindra Bank. The variance is higher in State Bank of India and lesser in Kotak Mahindra Bank. The coefficient of variation is higher in Axis bank therefore showcasing more volatility and less in Kotak Mahindra Bank showcasing a lesser volatility.

V. RESULTS OF MULTIPLE LINEAR REGRESSION

In order to either accept or reject the below mentioned hypothesis the Multiple linear regression test has been conducted.

- H_{01} : There is no significant increase in the risk and return of the banking sector stocks.
- H_{a1} : There is significant increase in the risk and return of the banking sector stocks.

Multiple linear regression analysis using Statistical Package for the Social Sciences software

The multiple linear regression was used to understand the relationship between the risk and return of the stocks. Where, return was considered as dependant variable and risk was considered as the independent variable which include beta value and the standard deviation of

the stock. The output of this test gives four tables namely, Variables Entered/Removed, Model Summary, ANOVA and Coefficients.

Table showing Variables Entered/Removed^a

Model	Variables Entered	Variables Removed	Method
1	Beta, Standard Deviation ^b		Enter
a. Dependent Variable: Average Returns			
b. All requested variables entered.			

Source: Author's calculation based on secondary data

Table Showing Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	0.728 ^a	0.529	0.059	7.2862
a. Predictors: (Constant), Beta, Standard Deviation				

Source: Author's calculation based on secondary data

Table Showing ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Significance
1	Regression	119.454	2	59.727	1.125	0.471 ^b
	Residual	106.177	2	53.089		
	Total	225.632	4			
a. Dependent Variable: AverageReturns						
b. Predictors: (Constant), Beta, StandardDeviation						

Source: Author's calculation based on secondary data

Table Showing Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Significance
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	2.403	14.707		0.163	0.885
	StandardDeviation	3.864	2.576	6.450	1.500	0.272
	Beta	-115.791	77.644	-6.413	-1.491	0.274

a. Dependent Variable: AverageReturns

Source: Author's calculation based on secondary data

Interpretation:

From the above table, Variables Entered/Removed table indicates the dependent and independent variable used in this analysis. The hypothesis tests that is there any significant increase in the risk and return of the banking sector stocks. In model summary table the “R” value, R square value and the adjusted R square value has been given. From the above table, the R square is .529 which indicates the independent variables that is the standard deviation and beta has made a 52.9% change in the dependent variable that is on the average return of the selected banking sector stocks. From the coefficients table the constant “B” was 2.403 which was the b_0 value. It defines the mean of the average return. The standard deviation has a positive beta value 6.450 which was positively related to the average returns and the beta value of beta-independent variable was -6.413 which was negatively related to the average returns. In this analysis the significant value of beta and standard deviation were .274 and .272 respectively, which was greater than 0.05. Hence the study accepts the null hypothesis. That is, there was no significant increase in the risk and return of the banking sector stocks.

Major Findings:

The study was conducted to analyse the risk and return and to examine the volatility of the selected banking sector stocks. The findings has been drawn on the basis of the objectives and hypothesis of the study. From the data collected and analysed the following findings have been observed:

- Among the five banks Industrial Credit and Investment Corporation of India bank has experienced higher average returns of 31.671 for a period of seven years from 2015 to 2022 with a moderate risk.
- The State Bank of India has higher risk as standard deviation of 45.833 compared with all other selected banking sector stocks.

- The State Bank of India has higher systematic risk based on its beta value of 1.395 compared with all other selected banking sector stocks during the period of study.
- Kotak Mahindra Bank has the lower risk based on standard deviation as 16.037 with a moderate return of 16.356, compared with other selected banks.
- The Kotak Mahindra Bank has lower systematic risk based on its beta value of 0.384 during the period of study.
- The study analysed that there was no significant increase in the risk and return of the banking sector stocks.
- During the period of study the Axis bank has the highest coefficient of variation of 3.802, hence it is more volatile in nature.
- The study analysed that there is a significant increase in the volatility of the banking sector stocks.

Suggestions:

This study helps potential investor to identify stocks from the banking sector and help them to take better banking decisions. The stocks with lower volatility have a lesser risk.

It is recommended that investors and the bank management who expect moderate return along with low risk on their investment may invest in stocks of Kotak Mahindra bank. On the other hand, if investors expect moderate risk with high returns, then they may invest in stocks of Industrial Credit and Investment Corporation of India bank. During the period of study, it was found that the stocks of Industrial Credit and Investment Corporation of India bank and Kotak Mahindra bank yield maximum returns and minimum risk respectively. Therefore, it is recommended that investors expecting maximum returns and minimum risk may invest in these stocks respectively. It recommended for the investors to go forward with similar calculations in order to create a desirable portfolio.

Conclusion:

The present study aimed at analysing the risk, return and the volatility of Housing Development Finance Corporation Limited bank, Industrial Credit and Investment Corporation of India bank, Kotak Mahindra Bank, State Bank of India and Axis bank stocks. The result of this study reveals that there was no significant increase in the risk and return of the banking sector stocks and there is a significant increase in the volatility of the banking sector stocks.

Comparing the five banking sector stocks considered in this study the return of the Industrial Credit and Investment Corporation of India banks were high for an average of seven years with the risk being high in State Bank of India and the Axis Bank being more volatile in nature. This was concluded by analysing the standard deviation, beta and the coefficient of variation to identify the risk and volatility of the stock.

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